

Investigating the Impact of Generative AI on the Modern Workspace

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11371946

Abstract---The potential paradigm-shifting disruption that Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) poses to individuals, groups, and organisations is significant. Although little is known about how new AI technologies will affect workers' performance and learning in the modern workplace, this could have a significant impact. This study examines several secondary sources to ascertain the effects of Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) in contemporary work environments. Using a machine-learning model and preexisting human content as a starting point, generative artificial intelligence (GAI) creates new content that mimics what humans create. The cognitive method that forms the basis of this model is behaviourism, which is founded on an already-existing body of knowledge.

As a result, the Internet now contains a vast amount of fresh data due to the quick expansion of GAI systems, which presents new difficulties for the existing computing and communication frameworks. This white paper analysed recent advances in cloud computing and artificial intelligence, respectively, and identified technical difficulties. In conclusion, this paper presents suggestions for additional large-scale uses of GAI and identifies future research possibilities in the contemporary workspace.

Keywords---Generative AI, ChatGPT, GitHub, LLMs.

I. INTRODUCTION

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GAI) even as a product of decades of software engineering, especially by integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) has become a groundbreaking field today due to its ability in effective content creation. This happens by GAI autonomously generating new content albeit not new as it is based on the content created by human beings before serving as a frame of reference through a library of different kinds of data such as text [1], images [3,8], audio [2], [3], text [5], [6], and even up to 3D objects [9], [3] which are used in Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) applications. Due to its ease in adaptability and integration, GAI has taken several applications such as Chat interactives models (examples include Chat-GPT [5] and Google Bard [5]), as text-to-image generation [4], [7], synthesis of text-to-speech (TTS) [2], and AI-empowered mixed reality (MR) which includes AR and VR have been widely used by consumers all over the globe. Even as the horizons of GAI expand in application, effectiveness, and efficiency its models now have to rely on deep neural networks such as the Large Language Models (LLMs) [11] and generative adversarial networks (GANs) [13] due to the increasing complexity of generative tasks by users. This increasing degree of complexity created a need for higher computational competency which was solved by cloud computing which utilised a centralized computational infrastructure to meet the requests of users. This consumes a significant amount of energy as the overlying computing framework is unsustainable and cost-inefficient especially when cloud servers experience high traffic resulting in high latency.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Research Methodology

[3] defines a systematic literature to be conducted in several stages such that data from secondary sources of information are gathered and analyzed for further research. This section followed to following steps in its literature review on “investigating the impact of Generative Artificial on the modern workspace”

I. Literature retrieval— This is the most crucial step in step in the process of literature review as it involves the data collection processes such as keyword and phrase selection and then inputting them into the Scopus database. For the study, some of the keywords used include “generative AI”, “workspace and AI”, and “ChatGPT and Worker”, amongst others. The result of this step produced materials from over 60 papers and journals.

II. Literature screening: This study used the PRISMA statement, a well-known and strict method for conducting systematic reviews and meta-analyses in literature reviews. To ensure the systematic identification, selection, and evaluation of the pertinent literature, this technique offered an ordered structural approach, which enhanced the accuracy and repeatability of the review process [15]. The material pool was then filtered after this procedure. from over 60 papers to about 30 papers with a 5-year timeline (2020 – 2024)

III. Content analysis: To find recurrent themes and patterns, a sizable body of material, especially academic journals, had to be carefully examined and arranged. The purpose of this study was to investigate how GAI affected the modern workspace, which is a hybrid workspace that combines traditional and remote work. A thorough understanding of the effects of generative artificial intelligence on teams, individuals, and organisations was made possible by this methodical approach.

IV. Bibliometric evaluation —Understanding academic trends was the aim of this study's bibliometric analysis, which methodically reviewed the academic literature but, in this case, concentrated on the citations and references inside papers. Emerging research fields, critical publications, prominent authors, and cooperative networks were all identified as a result of this procedure.

The white paper adopted this approach to ensure a comprehensive and accurate assessment of the research.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Recently, the field of Artificial intelligence has experienced rapid growth, especially with the release of open-source tools such as ChatGPT, GitHub Copilot, and DALL-E which are based on Generative Artificial Intelligence and Large Language Models. These tools are essentially based on machine learning technologies which are utilized to generate content—such as text, images, music, or video from a pre-existing library of data. This section provides a background on GAI, its AI system design given Human Resource Management, and potential economic implications.

AI SYSTEM DESIGN IN THE MODERN WORKSPACE

This paper reviewed research by [17], which worked with the GAI predictive response model for customer service interactions. The study went further to combine a recent version of Chat-GPT with other machine learning algorithms with a focus on customer service interactions. The GAI model was trained using a large data set of customer-agent conversations which were categorized into several categories. These categories that formed the library were based on topics of the conversation, outcome, and quality of the agent such that positive outcomes were referenced in order of how long it took to successfully resolve each problem. The GAI was further trained

to identify higher predictive patterns by identifying empathy in the discourse of the identified successful calls [12], this led to the provision of appropriate technical documentation and the limitation of unprofessional language. This additional step mitigated some of the concerns associated with relying on LLMs to generate text. On deployment to assist agents, the GAI model generates two main types of output:

- I. Real-time suggestions for how agents should respond to customers
- II. A reference link to the data firm's internal documentation for relevant technical issues or frequently asked questions library.

In both cases, recommendations are based on a Historical record of conversations. In one such example, the model learned that phrases like "I can assist you with this!" and "Happy to help you get this fixed ASAP" are associated with positive outcomes. It should be noted that [13] study considered GAI as an augment to the workspace and not a replacement giving the agent/worker full discretion to follow the suggestions of the AI model. Furthermore, the system does not provide suggestions when it has insufficient training data for that situation. In these situations, the agent/worker must respond on their own.

TECHNICAL PRIMER ON LARGE LANGUAGE MODELS

Looking more closely at the GAI framework, large language models (LLMs) are an important step because of their foundation in cognitive theory, which simulates human mental processes. LLMs are neural network models made to handle sequential data, claims [18]. Using a vast corpus or library of text data, an LLM is trained to predict the next word in a sequence given what has come before it. (this could be from sources such as defined libraries, Wikipedia, digitised books, or sections of the Internet). This method creates new text that is both semantically and grammatically meaningful by using a probability formula that predicts the statistical co-occurrence of terms. Recent advancements in generative AI have been primarily fueled by four factors:

- I. Scale computation
- II. Model architecture
- III. The capacity to "pre-train" with substantial volumes of unlabeled data
- IV. Constant improvement of training methods

Computing Scale - this is an essential factor as the quality of the model built is strongly dependent on it, the reason being that it determines the number of resources to be allocated to it for training such as the size of the dataset, the number of model parameters, and even the amount of processing power required for training [22]. As a result, it has been seen that GAI development companies are investing more money in expanding this scale. An example of this can be found in the well-known GPT-3 model, which had 175 billion data parameters and was trained on 300 billion tokens, costing roughly \$5 million in computing expenses alone. In contrast, the next model, the GPT-4 model, is estimated to have 1.8 trillion parameters and was trained on 13 trillion tokens, resulting in an astonishing \$65 million in computing costs alone.

Model design: Positional encoding and self-attention are two prior major innovations that are used by modern LLMs in terms of design. The purpose of positional encodings is to track or record the word order within an input. Simultaneously, self-attention allocates a weight value to every word within the context of the complete input text. When combined, these methods allow models to accurately represent long-range semantic links found in an input text, even when the text is divided into smaller pieces and analysed concurrently [16].

Pretrained Ability – LLMs can also be trained or developed on large amounts of data that can be gathered from public sources such as Wikipedia, Quora, and Reddit. These sources are used due to the availability of large unlabeled data when compared to sorted or labeled data. Also, it is important to note that the size of the data influences the quality of the natural language learned from the raw data. When trained on large amounts of unlabeled raw data, the resulting model becomes more adaptable to several applications. An instance of this is in the grammatical and semantic relationship of words when trained from a text library unlike labeled data trained with explicit instructions.

Continuous refinements in training techniques -One example arising from this feature is the Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (GPT) family of models, whose fast developing capabilities have garnered significant media attention. This can be achieved by further optimising an already-existing general-purpose LLM to produce output that aligns with the settings' priorities [19, 22]. An application's user engagement could be monitored by repurposing a model that was trained to create content for social media. However, it is advised that human evaluators be added to the models to rate the outputs and prioritise the GAI/LLM's desired responses. The combined effect of these advances is a significant improvement in the GAI/LLM model performance.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

To sum up, the use of Generative AI (GAI) in various organisations represents a noteworthy advancement in digital transformation and creative enhancement, affecting fields such as communications, engineering, and academics. Although GAI has a positive impact on increasing productivity at work, its use presents ethical questions that require careful evaluation of the social and cultural ramifications of the technology as well as adherence to safety regulations and laws. Meticulous management is necessary for the responsible and effective usage of GAI.

V. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

This review, drawing insights from approximately 30 Scopus-sourced publications, extensively examines GAI's impact in various areas. Looking towards future research, critical areas for enhancing employee productivity through GAI have been identified. These areas span different areas and demand careful investigation to fully realise GAI's promise of boosting productivity at work and encouraging creativity.

Extensive research on the necessary knowledge and abilities for researchers and educators to use GAI is desperately needed in the field of professional development in education. This entails assessing already offered training courses and putting forth creative models that blend pedagogical techniques with technical expertise. Developing methodological strategies to lessen biases in GAI applications is necessary to address the problem of AI bias and discrimination. In this sense, interdisciplinary research that combines social science insights with AI technology may present intriguing answers.

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